

ANALYSIS OF CARBON FIBER COMPOSITE COIL AND RING FOR OFFLOADING HOSES UNDER CRUSHING LOAD VIA COMPUTATIONAL MODELLING

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ABSTRACT

Offloading hoses are used in several production & storage systems, for example, Early Production System (EPS) and Catenary Anchor Leg Mooring (CALM). These hoses are comprised of rubber layers, reinforcement plies and a coil/ring component. If this hose is bent until collapse of the circular section (kink), the steel coil within it undergoes plastic deformation, with obstruction of the section that will render the hose useless. More recent design projects for hoses may include the use of advanced materials, which may be lighter and stronger, such as polymer composite materials. This study aims to investigate the substitution of the coil steel traditionally used as load-bearer component of offloading hoses (20" diameter and 35' length) for composite materials. Tensile, compressive and shear properties of various carbon fiber laminates were evaluated. A finite element model considering a central section of the hose was built to allow comparison of the crushing load of steel and composite coils and rings, and a radial compressive displacement of 100 mm was applied opposite to the fixed region. The numerical results of maximum crushing load for different coil diameters varied according to the selected failure criteria (Tsai-Hill, Tsai-Wu, Hashin and multicontinuum, MCT). Numerical modelling of the steel coil showed plastic strain for a compressive load of 23.8 kN. Square, circular and semi-circular cross sections were evaluated for composite coil/ring specimens of similar cross-section area. The composite coil with circular cross-section and the composite ring with square section displayed maximum experimental compressive load of 28.4 and 33.6 kN, respectively, which were close to those obtained with the MTC criterion. The composites showed lower stiffness than the steel coil, but the overall analysis indicated specific stiffness and strength of the composite components around, respectively, 1.6–2.9 and 4.5–6.9 times higher than that of the steel component.

1 INTRODUCTION

For oil transportation, specific systems are used according to the particular application needs. Among the most used, one can find the Early Production System (EPS), where the platform connects directly with the Shuttle Tanker, and the Catenary Anchor Leg Mooring (CALM), where a monobuoy distributes to other hose lines [1]. These hoses are a type of Bonded Flexible Pipe. The two main families include underwater and floating hoses and they are both built around a cylindrical mandrel, which ensures the inner diameter. In this mandrel, flanges are positioned at the ends, and between the flanges, layers of various materials (fibers, steel mesh, rubber, etc.) are subsequently deposited, being the last layer the final cover [2].

The main components of the floating hose used in the oil industry are flange, nipple, rubber layers, reinforcement plies and the coil/ring. Each component has a specific role, which involves design and construction with different characteristics. The load-bearing component is a wire coil with crushing and torsional strength. The coil is usually a solid steel bar, which is continuously applied on the hose following a specific diameter, pitch and size, in order to control the mechanical properties [3]. The steel coil has high weight and the steel may reach plastic strain. Therefore, the development of lightweight structures, with high strength and great load share is considered strategic.

Among the various manufacturing processes to produce polymer composite parts, pultrusion and filament winding can be highlighted due to characteristics like high accuracy in fiber positioning, high-fiber volume content, low void content and process automation. These processes are currently capable of producing rings and coil parts. However, the behavior of these components is still complex to predict.

There are several ways to estimate strength of a composite material, such as those based on the following failure criteria: Maximum strain, Maximum stress, Tsai-Hill [4], Tsai-Wu [5], Hashin [6], Christensen [7] and Puck [8]. It should be emphasized that each failure criteria is simply used to identify the initiation of failure at the integration points of the computational model. Once failure initiation occurs at an integration point, the default instantaneous degradation method is used for stiffness degradation. Other criterion developed in recent years is called Multicontinuum Theory (MCT) [9,10], which is a progressive failure analysis related to the independent matrix and fiber failures.

This work evaluates the potentialities and drawbacks of replacing the coil steel traditionally used as load-bearer component of 20" diameter oil offloading hoses by carbon/epoxy composites based on numerical modeling and experimentation related to a crushing test.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Material Testing

Tests were carried out on carbon/epoxy samples with 60% fiber volume fraction. The tensile tabbed coupons (fibers oriented at 0°) had dimensions of 250 mm length, 15 mm width and 1.5 mm thickness, according to ASTM D3039. An Instron 3382 testing machine equipped with axial and transverse extensometers was used to determine tensile modulus and Poisson's ratio, as shown in Figure 1. The testing speed was 2 mm / min.

For compression testing of the samples with fibers oriented at 0° , the test coupons had: 140 mm length, 12 mm width and 1.5 mm thickness. Test was conducted according to ASTM D6641 with a CLC device and at 1.3 mm/min cross-head speed. This test was used to obtain the longitudinal compressive strength of the composite.

Double V-notched samples were used for shear testing, according to ASTM D7078. The device was coupled to the machine to apply shear loading to the samples. A data acquisition system HBM Spider 8 600 Hz was used to obtain shear modulus (G_{12}) based on rosette strain gage readings. ILSS short beam tests were performed according to ASTM D2344. A flexural load was applied to the curved samples. An ILSS device was coupled to the testing machine, and the test was performed at 1 mm/min to obtain the out-of-plane shear strength (τ_{13}).

2.2 Crush test Ocimf 2009

A section prototype with 500 mm length from the hose body was modelled. A rectangular surface with 400 mm width was used as section support. A pre-load was applied until the entire surface was in contact with the section. The outer diameter along the plane perpendicular to the load was measured. 15-load increments were applied with the same size step and the outer diameter of the plane perpendicular to the load was recorded at each increment. Finally, the permanent (plastic) and temporary (elastic) deflections were calculated.

Figure 1: A. Instron 3382 testing machine, B. region for coupled test device, C. tensile device, D. CLC compression device, E. V-Notched Rail shear device and F. Short beam device.

2.3 Finite element modeling

Structural modelling was carried out via finite element method using commercial software Abaqus/CAE® 6.13. The Autodesk Simulation Composite Analysis 2015 plugin was used to evaluate the failure criteria. The plugin operates with the finite element software through a Fortran subroutine UMAT (User Material). This auxiliary program significantly improves speed and accuracy of the model building process.

The stress vs strain curve of the elastomer, which makes up the section filling, was experimentally obtained [11] and interpolated using hyperelastic Arruda-Boyce's model. The stress vs strain curve of the polyester cords was also experimentally obtained [12], being interpolated using the hyperelastic Marlow's model. The steel, i.e. the original coil, was treated as a linear isotropic material, having typical mechanical properties [13].

Firstly, the finite element model results were compared to experimental results of crushing tests with a steel coil (diameter: 12.7 mm). Then, analyses with composite coils were performed comparing the variation in diameter of the section, 10, 11, 12, 12.7 and 14 mm. Failure was evaluated using the Tsai-Hill, Tsai-Wu, Hashin and MTC criteria. Six different configurations were performed, using circular section 12.7 mm diameter, square section (side: 11.25 mm) and semi-circular section (radius: 9 mm). All coils and rings were equally spaced.

The model was meshed using 3D-solid elements. For the elastomer body, 6750 elements with 8 linear nodes – hexahedral hybrid (C3D8RH) were used. For the reinforcement plies, 35825 elements with 4 linear node – quadratic (SFM3D4) were used. Lower and upper supports were defined as rigid surfaces. To verify accuracy of the coil mesh, mesh-refinement analyses were performed with different numbers of hexahedral and tetrahedral elements as shown in Figure 2 based on the stabilization of the crushing load. It can be noted in this figure that crushing load does not vary significantly for a minimum of 9400 hexahedral elements. For the tetrahedral elements, stability occurred for a minimum of 57490 elements. The crushing load was calculated as a function of the stress in the coil. Calculation was based on C3D20R or C3D10M, which represent the coil/rings. The element near the supports was selected since it showed maximum stress.

Figure 2: Test of mesh convergence for the steel coil.

The difference in the converged crushing loads between the elements was 4.6%. The element used to compose the support component was 20 node quadratic hexahedral (C3D20R), due to the smaller number of elements and lower crushing load, but mainly because this type of element shows more accurate numerical results than tetrahedral elements. The number of elements varied in each studied configuration, as shown in Table 1.

Nomenclature	Configuration	Cross section	Dimensions (mm)	Weight (kg)	Elements	Nodes
SCC12	<i>Steel coil</i>	Circular	$\varnothing=12.7$	20	9400	70521
CCC12	<i>Composite coil</i>	Circular	$\varnothing=12.7$	3.8	15732	118011
CCSC18		Semi-circular	$\varnothing=18$		35190	207268
CCS11		Square	11.25×11.25		15548	116631
CRC12	<i>Composite rings</i>	Circular	$\varnothing=12.7$	3.7	57186	300756
CRSC18		Semi-circular	$\varnothing=18$		41760	81084
CRS11		Square	11.25×11.25		16944	45537

Table 1: Different coils and rings investigated in this work.

The hose section was fixed in the lower support. In the upper support, displacements and rotations in all directions were fixed, except in 2 direction, where a displacement of 100 mm was assigned. The material of the load-bearer component was modelled as transversely isotropic, with the fiber direction following the axial direction along the component. Figure 3 shows details of the FE model.

Figure 3: Details of the finite element model used to simulate crushing load.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Mechanical properties of composite material

Table 2 shows the results of tensile, compressive and shear properties of the 1-D composite. The carbon/epoxy samples showed satisfactory tensile results. The longitudinal compressive strength of the composite was 54% lower than the longitudinal tensile strength. These results were used as input in the simulations.

<i>Elastic constants</i>	<i>Longitudinal modulus – E_{11} (GPa)</i>	116.3 ± 4.7
	<i>Poisson's coefficient - ν_{12}</i>	0.32 ± 0.02
	<i>Shear modulus - G_{12} (GPa)</i>	4.05 ± 0.56
<i>Strengths</i>	<i>Longitudinal tensile strength – σ_{11}^T (MPa)</i>	1878.1 ± 101.2
	<i>Longitudinal compressive strength – σ_{11}^C (MPa)</i>	873.0 ± 99.0
	<i>In-plane shear strength - τ_{12} (MPa)</i>	68.3 ± 2.6
	<i>Out-of-plane shear strength - τ_{13} (MPa)</i>	75.8 ± 6.1

Table 2: Mechanical properties of the representative 1-D carbon/epoxy laminate.

3.2 Crush tests: Compressive load vs. Displacement

Figure 4 shows the compressive load versus displacement curve for the experimental crush test with steel (diameter: 12.7 mm). At the beginning of the curve, the load-displacement relationship is linear. For higher displacement, e.g. 25 mm, a reaction force of 28 kN is noticed. For a displacement of 25 mm, permanent strain started to occur. A reduction in section stiffness is expected after 28 kN due to difference between the curves shown.

Figure 4: Compressive load vs displacement curve of the crushing test using a steel coil.

3.3 Effect of the diameter cross section of the composite coil

The effect of the diameter of the cross-section on the crushing load was studied for the carbon/epoxy coil, as shown in Figure 5. The 12.7 mm diameter coil showed similar crushing load than the steel coil of the same diameter. All criteria yielded linear variation of the load with the diameter. The criteria based on first ply failure (Tsai-Hill and Tsai-Wu) showed lower load than those based on progressive failure criteria (Hashin and MCT).

The crushing load is very sensitive to the change in diameter. The coil with 10 mm diameter resisted a load of 19.4, 16.5, 14.5 and 14.1 for the Hashin, MCT, Tsai-Hill and Tsai-Wu failure criteria, respectively. A variation of 1 mm in diameter yields a difference in crushing load around 23% for all criteria. Besides, the crushing load varies on average 28% between the Tsai-Wu criteria and Hashin, the minimum and maximum values, respectively. Hashin shows the largest value because this failure criterion does not incorporate the longitudinal stress component in the fiber direction (S_{11}) in the estimate of matrix failure.

Figure 5: Numerical results for the composite coil with different diameters section.

3.4 Effect of the cross section geometry

Figure 6 shows the numerical results of the damage evolution of the coil with circular cross section (diameter: 12.7 mm) using the MCT failure criteria with the failure index SDV1. Values of SDV1 between 0-1 indicate that there is no failure, between 1-2, matrix failure occurs, and between 2-3, fiber and matrix failure occur. It can be noted that up to 50 mm displacement, fiber failure occurs and, for higher displacement, global failure of the structure occurs. Failure always occurs in the region where the coil tends to increase in diameter due to the crushing load.

Figure 6: 3D Image of the damage in the composite coil (diameter: 12 mm).

Figure 7 shows the numerical results of the crushing load for six different geometries of the support component with carbon fiber. The compressive load vs displacement curve shows that the rings with square section (side: 11.25 mm) (CRS11) show the highest energy to failure, about 426% higher than the steel coil. The coil (CCSC18) and rings (CRSC18) with semi-circular section with 18 mm diameter show a crushing load lower than the steel coil (SCC12), but with higher displacement. The rings with circular cross-section (diameter: 12.7 mm), the coil with circular section (diameter: 12.7 mm) and the coil with square section (side: 11.25 mm) show similar curves, with crushing load and displacement of around 30 kN and 50 mm, respectively. The composite components show energy to failure around 288% higher than the steel coil.

Moreover, based on Figure 7, experimental data and the numerical model for the steel coil show the beginning of the permanent strain. The model was able to generate valid approximations for the crushing load of the hose section, around 23.8 kN for those test conditions. After that, plastic strain occurs, corresponding to a yield stress of 700 MPa. For a load of 28 kN, the coil reaches a maximum tensile stress of 830 MPa, corresponding to a displacement of 21 mm at yield.

The stress components were evaluated for the first failed element. Comparing in-plane shear stress (S_{12}), out-of-plane shear stress (S_{13} and S_{23}) and normal stress (S_{33}), S_{13} showed the highest contribution to failure for all examined criteria, as shown in Table 3. Thus, the expected failure mode would be matrix shear or delamination. These results are in accordance with those of Mahfuz et al. [14] and Bazhenov [15], which report that the main failure in the longitudinal compression of rings is due to delamination. The second highest stress contributing to the failure is the longitudinal compressive stress S_{11}^c .

Figure 7: Compressive load vs displacement curves of steel and composite specimens.

Stress Component	MCT		Hashin		Tsai-Wu		Tsai-Hill	
	Value (MPa)	S_{ij}/σ_{ij}						
S_{11}^T	545.0	29%	926.0	49%	148.0	8%	154.0	8%
S_{11}^C	593.0	68%	195.0	22%	581.0	67%	592.0	68%
S_{22}^T	5.6	0%	16.0	1%	7.1	1%	8.1	1%
S_{22}^C	10.0	3%	5.8	1%	10.9	3%	11.3	3%
S_{33}^T	14.8	1%	44.0	3%	18.7	1%	19.5	1%
S_{33}^C	24.0	6%	22.0	6%	8.4	2%	9.4	2%
S_{12}	8.1	12%	8.3	12%	6.1	9%	7.1	10%
S_{13}	62.7	83%	50.5	67%	60.0	79%	62.2	82%
S_{23}	4.9	10%	7.5	15%	3.9	8%	4.2	8%

Table 3: Stress state of the first failed element.

Based on the MCT's results, Table 4 shows the specific stiffness and strength (i.e. in relation to density) for the different configurations. The specific stiffness and strength for steel coil is only 145 N.mm²/kg and 3248 N.mm³/kg, respectively, whereas the lowest specific stiffness and strength obtained for the composite components are 231 N.mm²/kg and 14666 N.mm³/kg, respectively, for the CRSC18.

Nomenclature	Configuration	Specific stiffness (N.mm ² /kg)	Specific strength (N.mm ³ /kg)
SCC12	Steel coil	145	3248
CCC12	Composite coil	394	19035
CCSC18		274	15370
CCS11		406	20330
CRC12		424	20844
CRSC18	Composite rings	231	14666
CRS11		353	22528

Table 4: Specific stiffness and strength of the various components.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study focused on the assessment of the load-bearing component, made of composite material (carbon fiber and epoxy), of an oil offloading hose under crushing load. The model was highly refined and showed good accordance with the available experimental results.

The numerical results, based on analysis with advanced failure criteria, have demonstrated that the load-bearing component based on composite material has a crushing strength equal or higher than that based on steel. In addition, the composite material improves load sharing due to the high level of displacement to failure, with energy to failure reaching 288-426% higher than that of the steel spiral, depending on the particular configuration.

The cross-section diameter of the coil affects the maximum crushing load, following a linear relationship for all failure criteria. Also, the out-of-plane shear stress (S_{13}) was found to be the main contributor to the failure, leading to delamination of the support component. The out-of-plane shear stress S_{23} and the normal stress S_{33} contributed less to the failure.

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